

Enhancing applied, interdisciplinary learning with online, interactive case history modules that bridge undergraduate geoscience courses

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Project Summary

Complex geoscience problems often cross disciplinary lines. As such, when students become professionals, they will be required to draw upon and connect concepts from a range of disciplines. However, students are given little institutional or instructional support to build this web of connected concepts; most courses are taught in isolation.

We propose to support students' exploration of these connections using multi-disciplinary touchstones that connect six courses across the disciplines of geology, geophysics, geological engineering and hydrogeology. We will develop these touchstones using interdisciplinary case histories: scientific narratives that begin with an applied problem, incorporate data and analyses, and conclude with inferences and solutions to the stated problem. This project will create online modules, with embedded interactive simulations, which enable students to examine the scientific concepts and connections between these concepts within the context of each case history. Interdisciplinary teams of students will be employed in the development of these modules.

Project Objectives

Why?

Real life problems are complicated; investigations and solutions require cooperation among experts in many disciplines. In the earth sciences, these problems include global warming, water resource management, site remediation from environmental pollution, exploration and production of resources including hydrocarbons and minerals. To tackle these problems, students must develop and practice interdisciplinary skills, which we define as the ability to think deeply about a problem from their discipline's perspective (e.g. hydrology, geophysics, geology, atmospheric science, engineering), draw connections between their expertise and that of neighbouring disciplines, be aware of the resources and approaches available to them from the neighbouring disciplines, and finally communicate across the disciplines to explore solutions.

We have three overall objectives for the enhancement of teaching and learning in EOAS: (1) To support students in their development of interdisciplinary competencies by creating a

case history framework that provides students opportunities to examine, interrogate, draw connections, and make inferences using data in the context of real-world problems; (2) To promote student driven exploration of concepts using embedded, interactive visualization tools; and (3) To accomplish (1) and (2) in a manner that is sustainable beyond this grant.

(1) Interdisciplinary Connections Using Case Histories

A case history is an applied scientific story that begins with the articulation of the problem to be solved, develops the observations and analyses, and ends with inferences that can be drawn as they pertain to the solution of the stated problem. These challenges often require concepts and resources from multiple disciplines in order to achieve a solution. For example, tracking and remediating a contaminant spill requires input from geology and hydrogeology to identify how and where the contaminant may flow, from geophysics to track the contamination using remote sensing, and from engineering to design a remediation strategy.

Case histories provide a range of opportunities for students' interdisciplinary engagement: context for investigating scientific concepts, analyzing data, assessing outcomes and conclusions, or reanalysis using new data. As such, modules can be incorporated within a lecture, lab, assignment, or Team Based Learning (TBL) activities.

(2) Learning Enhancement Through Interactivity

The case history modules will include interactive web-based applications; allowing students to experiment with, explore, and practice skills related to geoscience concepts in a way that is not possible with pencil and paper alone. By integrating interactive simulations that allow students to interrogate the influence of various parameters and rapidly visualize resulting changes, all within the context of these case histories, we aim to put students in the driver's seat for the exploration of concepts.

(3) Sustainability, Accessibility, and Student Contributions

Ensuring sustainability of our project outcomes and encouraging student contributions are primary motivators in our implementation strategy. Case history modules will be hosted online and be open access, version controlled, and documented. These practices allow modules to be adapted by future instructors and remain accessible to students long after they finish their courses. Our work plan is formulated such that these essential elements for sustainability are designed, implemented, and tested, with input from students, and with a vision of encouraging development of new modules that enable undergraduate contribution.

Project Work Plan, Timeline & Milestones

How do you...

- encourage students to connect concepts across courses?
- do this without overhauling the curriculum?
- promote student-driven exploration and engagement with concepts?
- involve students and encourage sustainable project growth?

Our approach

We do not focus on individual courses, and do not expect instructors to drive this process. We focus on linking courses using case histories, and foster a community of student contributors, guided by instructors. We prototype and build online and in the open. We put interactive simulations in the hands of students. We follow best practices. We document everything. We build a framework for using case histories to catalyze interdisciplinary connections. We set an example for open access contribution that will inspire faculty, graduates, and undergraduates to engage and to contribute.

Building upon past successes

We are building from a foundation of work and experience, including: (a) development for EOSC 350 in the form of a digital textbook, (which started over a decade ago and we have revamped over the past year under an SCLT development grant: <http://gpg.geosci.xyz>), along with a suite of interactive modules to enable students to explore and visualize concepts in geophysics. (b) Visible Geology, an award winning open geologic modelling platform with over 12,000 worldwide student users per month (350,000 students over the last three years), developed by co-applicant Rowan Cockett. Visible Geology is used in a number of courses across EOAS to provide students with the resources to visualize and explore geologic concepts. (c) Catalyzing and supporting multi-university communities of developers (20+) on open source software and textbook development (<http://simpeg.xyz>, <http://github.com/ubcgif>).

The experience gained, including feedback from an international community, and the resources previously developed, contribute to the plan herein.

The Plan

We have identified six courses that can be brought together through the development of three case histories with the goal of impacting students across at least 4 of the 7 degree programs in EOAS. The identified instructors are enthusiastic about the vision and net benefits of this project, but are understandably cautious about personal commitments and potential impacts upon their course content. These early interactions have been seminal in our development of a practical work plan outlined below. We must create the ability to grow this resource, and a community of resource developers that is self-sustaining. We need,

and have started development of, a framework for teaching and learning using interdisciplinary case histories that can be built upon by a community of students who are guided by instructors. As such, these resources must be developed and deployed in the open using Creative Commons (CC BY 4.0) and MIT licenses as appropriate.

Case history modules will be implemented in a four-stage process:

1) Identify:

The PI's and TLF will work with instructors to identify case histories with linkages that support and enrich their courses. These case histories must include key concepts that align with, and provide context to, concepts in the course. Instructors will need to have a vision for how the case history, or elements of it, may be incorporated into course material, such as lectures, labs, assignments, and team-based activities, without unduly adding to the course load.

2) Prototype:

The PI's, TLF, an Instructional Designer, and a working-group of graduate and undergraduate students with the appropriate backgrounds will outline a functional prototype for the case history module, include the layout, organization and explanation of concepts as well as sketches of interactive simulations. Prior to module development, feedback and input will be solicited from instructors. The development and outlining process will be documented, following open development practices to ensure it is an easily accessible resource and will serve as a template for future module development.

Where and how case histories are deployed and integrated into existing course material will be key details that we address in the Identify and Prototype stages and appropriate actions will be taken to revamp existing assignments.

3) Develop:

The working-group of students will develop the case history modules, alongside a domain-specific programmer who will develop or adapt existing software for the interactive simulation tools. The PI's will initiate best practices for capturing the knowledge and process of developing a module by setting up repositories (e.g. GitHub) that are linked to resources for writing documentation (e.g. ReadTheDocs). Documentation is a budgeted task and recognised as a critical component.

Prior to initial deployments, a focus group with undergraduate students will be used to beta-test the modules.

4) Deploy:

Throughout the process outlined above, we will solicit feedback from instructors to ensure engagement and applicability. The case history modules will be launched on the web,

requiring little to no technical overhead from the instructors to deploy them in the intended courses. For the initial deployments, the PI's and TLF will be involved to support and document the process. TAs facilitating these courses will have been prepared, using budgeted funds, for any additional training necessary.

Assessment will be completed by the TLF and is part of the deployment strategy. This is expanded upon in the evaluation criteria section of this grant.

Timeline & Milestones:

The module development plan will be replicated three times in a staggered start over the project lifetime. Identification work for CH1 (Case History 1) has been started and will continue to be advanced prior to the start date of April 1 for this grant.

CH1) Start: Sept 2015, Deploy: Sept 2016, Sept 2017 - Courses: 350/331, Students: 100

CH2) Start: April 2016, Deploy: Jan 2017 - Courses: 240/329, Students: 180

CH3) Start: Jan 2017, Deploy: Sept 2017, Jan 2018 - Courses: 110/116, Students: 700

People:

TLF: leadership and facilitation in development, deployment and assessment of the case history modules.

UAs and 6 GAAs:

- 2 Leads for Develop; 2 Team for Prototype; 2 OnDeck for Identify
- Lead or Team GAAs will be TAs in the targeted courses and help bring these resources into deployment when TAing the course
- OnDeck GAAs are there to identify and learn the process prior to taking the lead in a subsequent CH
- UAs are in a similar role to the Team GAAs

Programmer (Domain specific, EOAS): implement interactive applications and numerical simulations

Targeted Instructors (2hrs/month, in-kind)

Expected Project Outcomes

The proposed project will have three major outcomes: (1) three touchstone case histories that are used in (at least) six courses across EOAS to increase students exposure to multidisciplinary content; (2) a framework, with documentation of the process, for open source module development and assessment; (3) a sustainability strategy for continued contribution of case history modules by interdisciplinary teams of students. These outcomes address the underlying project goals of contributing to the enhancement of

teaching and learning by: (a) supporting students in their development of interdisciplinary competencies, (b) engaging students using novel web based simulation, and (c) creating a sustainable hub for continued development that will grow past its initial conception as students and instructors continue to contribute.

In detail, the expected project outcomes are generally broken into five categories that either contribute to the product or document the process:

1) Three connected, online case histories

- which are provided in a connected modular form rather than a linear, static PDF textbook. They combine the context of the case history, explanations of the fundamental concepts and questions/exercises to guide student exploration.

2) Supporting interactive simulations,

- which consist of: (a) open source numerical code to run simulations and produce the data to be visualized and (b) the interactive, visual interface for deploying the numerical simulations, leveraging the open-source Jupyter Notebook.
- software documentation

3) Documentation and commentary on the process of creating the modules, including guidelines on best practices, templates for contributing to the modules, and suggestions for improvement the module development process.

4) Assessment reports on how these modules improved student engagement and stimulated cross-disciplinary connections.

- success will be determined by engagement (student and instructor) and utility (as determined by the assessment reports)

5) Documentation on how the modules were used in courses (completed by instructors or by the PI's following interviews with instructors) and qualitative course surveys.

All content, simulations, and interactive applications will be open source and developed under modern version control. These development practices will help ensure that the modules are not only sustained, but allow us to invite other contributors to join with a low barrier to entry. Accessing and engaging the global and professional geoscience communities, who are well funded, is part of the sustainability plan.

The project also creates the potential for future studies: the interactive simulations allow for rich analytics to be collected on student interaction (engagement pattern data). This interaction data, coupled with an assignment with a clear goal, can support students metacognition to show how they solved problems relative to other students or experts. These goals are outside the scope of the current proposal, however, we will remain in conversations with SCLT about possible academic partnerships that can be made to study these unique insights and pursue these if, and when, applicable.

Project Benefits

Interdisciplinary Connections

Students graduating in many of UBC's current programs are well-equipped to solve problems confined to their area of expertise but they falter when working in multidisciplinary teams because of unfamiliarity with the scientific concepts and the general lexicon used in other areas. The case history modules developed through this project will be an accessible, interactive resource for students to investigate interdisciplinary links. Students will examine the same case history from multiple perspectives throughout their undergraduate courses and be exposed to connections with other courses and concepts they may not formally take during their degree. The explicit connections that are demonstrated through this project will exemplify the connected interdisciplinary nature of geoscientific concepts. These modules will provide a range of opportunities for student exploration from examining scientific concepts in the context of an applied problem, to drawing connections and formulating strategies for reaching a solution to a complex geoscientific problem. Having these resource accessible and online means students will have the opportunity to revisit and explore these concepts at different depths over the course of their careers.

EOAS is a collection of geoscientists from multiple disciplines (geology, geophysics, atmospheric sciences, physical and biological oceanography, planetary physics). It has long been a departmental goal to have more communication between these groups but the current structure of the department with multiple programs and specialized research areas has impeded interdisciplinary growth. Our approach of using case histories, with student and faculty development, can be a catalyst for opening up meaningful interdisciplinary engagement.

Accessible & Interactive

We provide these resources in a manner that is accessible to students and promotes exploration; it is not a linear textbook nor simply a collection of linked, disjoint pages, but a coherent, curated, web-based resource with connections between concepts. It is open source and hosted online, meaning it can serve as a resource for students during their degree and later in their professional careers.

These concepts are supported by interactive simulations. The simulation tools are resources for students to interrogate data and models in a visual manner. They include 3D visualization tools, such as Visible Geology, to help build students' ability to conceptualize spatial relationships. They also include numerical simulation tools which provide a means of visually interrogating the role of various parameters in a mathematical or physical model. Simulation tools allow students to interrogate input parameters and to rapidly visualize the outputs. They are rich way to interact, explore, and build intuition about complex systems.

Student Contributions

This project is driven by students with guidance from instructors. The working groups of students developing these modules will be composed of graduate and undergraduate students from a range of disciplines across EOAS. They will work in multidisciplinary teams, and in doing so gain practical, hands-on experience communicating and problem-solving with peers across disciplines. In this process, they will be creating and contributing to educational resources for use by their peers. Contribution is an essential part of being a citizen in a scientific community, and this is an opportunity for students to engage in this process during their own educational careers.

Evaluation Criteria

Our evaluation strategy addresses the quality of the resources we produce, and the impact of these resources on student learning.

To address the quality of the case histories we produce, we will draw on the disciplinary knowledge of our Department's faculty to identify and approve content. We will also use CTLT's quality enhancement checklists and instructional design support to incorporate best practices for blended and online learning into our case histories.

To determine the impact of our resources on student learning we will assess (1) the development of students' interdisciplinary thinking, and (2) the degree of student engagement with the case-history online materials. We will focus our evaluation efforts on the former while attending to the latter.

We will assess the development of students' interdisciplinary thinking using the following criteria (Boix, Mancilla & Duraising, 2007; Golding & Baik, 2013):

A. (Multi)disciplinary grounding: Are students drawing from and grounding their observations, analyses, and conclusions in multiple relevant disciplines? Are they expanding the disciplines from which they draw resources, and are they using other discipline's resources appropriately?

Key indicators include: the number of disciplines referenced and the appropriateness of the references.

B. Interdisciplinary advancement: Are students advancing their understanding by linking, translating, and/or integrating relevant disciplines? Are students going beyond describing different disciplinary contributions to comparing the contributions or synthesizing those contributions into new insights?

C. Interdisciplinary reflection: Are students demonstrating awareness of distinct disciplinary contributions, limitations, and conflicts in their disciplinary course work? Are they reflecting on the processes of integrating disciplinary concepts and data?

Key indicators for B and C include: The number and type of connectors student use between the disciplines (e.g. “is related to”, “contributes to”, “in contrast”, etc...); evidence of students’ use of integrative structures (e.g. graphical representations, models, metaphors) to deepen the complexity of their analyses.

Our analysis will involve comparing the content of students’ written work completed after interacting with the case histories with comparable assignments completed at the start of a unit and/or, where possible, without the case history modules. We intend to build this evaluation into existing, or easily implemented course assignments. While the exact nature of these assignments can only be determined as the project progresses, candidate assignments including specimen (rock, graphic, or image) description, problem definition (“what do you know and what do you need to know about ____ in order to determine _____.”), and structured concept mapping. Similar assessments will also be used to evaluate the progress of interdisciplinary competencies among the working group of students before, during and after being involved with the development of the modules.

We will also measure student engagement by tracking the uptake, use, and reach of our case histories over time using standard, anonymized analytics.

In the long term, it will be important to evaluate the impact of students’ multiple engagements with a single case history through different courses and over time. A full evaluation of this longer-term impact is beyond the scope of this proposal, but planning will be initiated.

Student Involvement

In the preparation of the proposal, student feedback on the current use of case histories and interactive resources in EOSC 350 have been paramount. We will continue soliciting feedback during the project using focus groups prior to module deployment. Feedback portals, with the option of submitting anonymously, will be set up for students (and instructors) to give feedback and input suggestions on the modules.

Our implementation strategy is designed to foster an interdisciplinary community of faculty and students and as such, relies heavily on undergraduate and graduate student involvement, with ~50% of the budget dedicated to students. This provides a unique professional development opportunity for these students to work in a cross-disciplinary team, interacting and communicating with faculty members and peers beyond a class setting. . We are proposing a project and development process that encourage students to reflect on concepts they have learned over their educational careers and draw connections between them. Contribution is an expectation of scientific citizenship. This project provides a place where students can take ownership and contribute to a valuable educational resource for their peers; fostering leadership, ownership, and purpose to exemplify the core values of UBC.

“UBC is a community of scholars whose essential functions are the pursuit and dissemination of knowledge and understanding through research and teaching. As part of this overall mission, UBC wishes to facilitate collaboration, the open exchange of ideas, and the creation, preservation, continual enhancement and utilization of materials incorporated into the delivery of courses of study at UBC” (Policy 81, UBC)

Special Classroom or Facilities Requirements

Comments on the interactive tools

All development will occur or be translated to Python, which is an interpreted, open-source language. For the interactive environment, we will use the Jupyter notebook, an interactive coding environment that supports HTML5 widgets. A suite of interactive tools has been developed and successfully deployed in EOSC 350.

Both the interactive nature of these notebooks and the ease of deployment into educational institutions is the target of major funding initiatives (<https://jupyter.org/>). To significantly lower the barrier to student accessibility, the optimal deployment strategy is through JupyterHub installed within UBC, requiring IT services; SCLT will explore this possibility.

When presenting to the core development team of the Jupyter project, they had not seen their environment used outside of teaching numerical techniques, especially not to a non-technical audience. This would be a pioneering effort for UBC.